

The Titration of Iron(II) with Hexacyanoferrate(III) in Strong Phosphoric acid Medium and its Application in the Determination of Iron(II)-Iron(III) Mixtures and Ores

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Iron(II) can be estimated with potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) or vice versa in 10-11*M* phosphoric acid medium potentiometrically. In the visual estimation of iron(II), *N*-phenylanthranilic acid, Barium diphenylamine sulphonate, *p*-ethoxychrysoidine and ferroin are used as reversible indicators. Iron(II) can be estimated in the iron(II)-Iron(III) mixtures and in ores. 30-300 mg. of hexacyanoferrate(III) with an average error of 0.16% and 10-40mg. of iron(II) with an average error of 0.44% are determined by potentiometric end-point. About 5-30mg. of iron(II) is determined with an average error of 0.2% by a visual method using different indicators.

WITTMANN¹ determined iron(II) ions potentiometrically with hexacyanoferrate(III) in 12-20 per cent hydrochloric acid. Kiboku² found that iron(II) can be titrated with hexacyanoferrate(III) in a solution of sodium diphosphate at pH 4.3-10. Hall and Flanigan³, determined Fe(II) ions in presence of iron(III) ions using E.D.T.A. Wieslaw Wisniewski and Halina Basinska⁴ determined iron(II) ions in 8 *M* HCl. medium both potentiometrically and visually using Ph₂NH as indicator. From the survey of literature it is evident that none has reported so far the titration of iron(II) with hexacyanoferrate(III) by a visual method in a colourless medium using indicators. In this paper the authors present the determination of iron(II) or potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) in 10-11 *M*, phosphoric acid medium potentiometrically and iron (II) alone by visual method using redox indicators. Its application for the determination of iron(II) in the mixtures of iron (II)-iron (III) and in ores is also extended successfully.

Experimental

Reagents :

Ferrous ammonium sulphate : 0.1 *M* solution is prepared by dissolving the needed weight of the substance (Analar) in 0.5 *M* H₂SO₄ and is standardised by standard potassium dichromate.

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) : 0.1 *M* standard solution is prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of the substance (Analar) and is standardised⁵ by standard sodium thiosulphate solution.

Ammonium ferric sulphate : 0.1 *M* solution is prepared by dissolving the sufficient amount of the substance (Analar) in 0.05 *M* H₂SO₄.

Indicators : 0.1% *N*-phenyl anthranilic acid (E. Merck), 0.1% B.D.A.S. 0.1% *p*-ethoxychrysoidine and 0.1% ferroin solutions are prepared.

Syrupy orthophosphoric acid (Pro-analysis, E. Merck).

All other reagents used are of analytical reagent grade quality.

Apparatus : The measurements are made with a KAYCEE potentiometer (Poona, India), a bright platinum rod was used as an indicator electrode and a saturated calomel electrode as the reference electrode. Electrical contact between the sample solution and the reference electrode was ensured with saturated potassium chloride salt bridge containing sintered glass ends.

The typical potentiometric titration curves of iron (II) with potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) and vice versa are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

The titration vessel is fitted with a rubber stopper having five holes, one for accommodating the micro burette, the second for the platinum electrode, the third for one limb of the salt bridge, the fourth and fifth for the inlet and outlet of the carbon dioxide. As the potential of Fe (III)/Fe (II) couple falls with an increase of phosphoric acid medium⁶, iron (II) is liable to a real oxidation. So the titration must be carried out under carbon dioxide atmosphere.

Recommended procedure : Appropriate amount of syrupy phosphoric acid is taken in the titration vessel to give an overall phosphoric acid concentration of 10 *M* in a total volume of 40 ml. carbon dioxide is passed through the contents for 10 min and then Fe(II) solution or potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) is added and potentials are recorded after adding a known volume of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) or iron(II).

Fig. 1. The typical potentiometric titration curves of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) with iron(II) and vice versa in 10M H₃PO₄.

(Δ—Δ) Potentiometric titration of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) with Fe(II) in 10M H₃PO₄.

(O—O) Potentiometric titration of Fe(II) with potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in 10M H₃PO₄.

A sharp potential break of 150 mV per 0.04 ml. of 0.1 M potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) was observed at the end-point. On the other hand a potential break of 130 mV per 0.04 ml. of 0.1 M iron(II) was observed during the titration of hexacyanoferrate(III) with iron (II). The potentials attain steady values in either case within one minute. Some typical results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—POTENTIOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF POTASSIUM HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) WITH Fe (II).

Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	% Error.
33.73	33.84	0.25
134.90	135.20	0.22
303.50	303.50	0.00
		Av. 0.16

Visual estimation: Visual titrations are also carried out in 10 M H₃PO₄ using N-phenyl anthranilic acid, B.D.A.S., *p*-ethoxychrysoidine and ferroin as indicators. The phosphoric acid concentration should not be less than 10 M or otherwise the blue colour appears.

Recommended procedure: In a 10 ml. beaker required amount of syrupy phosphoric acid is taken. Carbon dioxide is passed through the contents for 10 min. Then an aliquot volume of iron(II) solution is taken and the titration is carried out with potassium

hexacyanoferrate(III) while passing carbon dioxide through the solution. The determinations are carried out using above indicators. Except *p*-ethoxychrysoidine all the indicators can be added in the beginning. A few typical results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Fe(II) WITH POTASSIUM HEXACYANOFERRATE(III).

Method.	Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	% Error
(a) Potentiometric.	9.833	9.788	0.45
	14.72	14.65	0.47
	39.25	39.09	0.40
			Av. 0.44
(b) Visual			
	(1) B. D. A. S. Indicator		
	5.674	5.663	0.19
	17.02	16.99	0.17
	28.37	28.34	0.10
			Av. 0.15
(ii) <i>p</i> -ethoxychrysoidine.	5.195	5.089	0.31
	18.73	18.68	0.26
	29.50	29.44	0.20
			Av. 0.26
(iii) N-phenyl anthranilic acid.	4.531	4.513	0.39
	15.32	15.32	0.00
	27.81	27.74	0.25
			Av. 0.21
(iv) Ferroin	2.799	2.787	0.42
	15.88	15.87	0.06
	28.83	28.77	0.20
			Av. 0.23

The method has been used for the determination of iron in iron (II)-iron (III) mixtures and in ores.

Determination of Fe(II)-Fe(III) mixture: In one aliquot Fe(II)-Fe(III) mixture is taken. Fe(II) is determined with potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in phosphoric acid medium as described above. In second aliquot the total amount of iron is determined after iron(III) is reduced to iron(II) by photochemical method⁷. The difference between the two titre values gives the volume of hexacyanoferrate(III) corresponding to the amount of iron(III). Thus iron(II)-iron(III) mixture can be differentially estimated. The results are represented in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DIFFERENTIAL TITRATION OF Fe(II) Fe(III) MIXTURES.

(a) Potentiometric determination			(b) Visual determination		
Amount of Fe(II) (mg)			Amount of Fe(III) (mg)		
Taken	Found	%Error	Taken	Found	%Error
16.93	16.86	0.41	31.01	30.96	0.16
25.41	25.34	0.27	29.61	29.56	0.24
31.77	31.71	0.18	10.33	10.28	0.48
Av. 0.29			Av. 0.29		
12.68	12.62	0.47	20.79	20.73	0.28
21.63	21.57	0.27	36.14	36.04	0.27
25.41	25.34	0.27	25.42	25.36	0.23
Av. 0.34			Av. 0.26		

Determination of iron in ores : About 1 g. of the ore is taken in 250 ml pyrex beaker and treated with about 20-30 ml of (1 : 1) hydrochloric acid. The ore that is taken by us for the estimation is digested until the particles are free from colour. Only carbon and silica particles are left undissolved and they are filtered off. The clear solution is made up to a known volume. Iron amount is determined after its reduction to Fe(II), by potentiometric and visual methods. The percentages of iron present in the ores are given in Table. 4.

TABLE 4—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF IRON IN ORES.

Sample.	Percent of iron by		
	Vanadate ⁷ method	Potential- metric	Visual
Sample 1. (Dalli-Rajahara Durg Dt., M.P.)	28.21	28.09	28.15
Sample 2. (Bailadilla, Baster Dt., M.P.)	66.50	66.32	66.40

Discussion

The visual method detailed above in strong phosphoric acid medium is quite interesting for it is not giving the usual intensely blue colour with hexacyanoferrate(III) which is supposed to be resulted during the titrations of iron(II) in pH or acid medium. The reaction is proceeding with hexacyanoferrate(III) straight away as an oxidising agent without forming the usual blue complex. At 10-11 M phosphoric acid concentration the titration mixture is not coloured though at lower acidities the blue complex appears. The titration using the above indicators are giving very sharp colour change and thus avoiding the medium of opting potentiometric method alone for such a determination. The investigation of the constitutional part of the formation of the white precipitate during the titration, escaping the usual expected formation of the blue complex is under study.

The potentiometric method of titration in phosphoric acid is also very smooth which do not involve any pH regulations, vapours of HCl at high concentrations and such other factors. The potentials are fairly stable and the method is advantageous relative to other existent methods in its simplicity and less tediousness. It is found from the results that a negligible amount of negative error is involved perhaps due to the interference of the dissolved oxygen which is not possible to be excluded by normal available methods for deoxygenations. The use of the potentiometric and visual methods given by the authors is also applied successfully in the estimation of iron in the mixtures of iron (II)-iron(III) and in ores.

Ba²⁺, Na⁺, Hg²⁺, K⁺, SO₄²⁻, glucose, sucrose xalate do not interfere in any concentrations both in potentiometric and visual titrations. As³⁺ and Mn²⁺ will interfere in all concentrations whereas the colour of the ions Co²⁺ and Ni²⁺ will interfere during the visual titrations.

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